

Crystal Structure of B site Ordered ABiLiTeO₆ (A=Ba, Sr) Dielectric Ceramics

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Abstract

Double perovskites are compounds of the type AA'BB'O₆ that have been widely studied for their vast structural as well as physical properties. Double perovskites exhibit interesting physical properties and are used as microwave dielectrics, ionic conductors, half metallic conductors, ferroelectrics, superconductors, photo-catalysts and host materials for luminescence centres etc. [1] In the present study, B-site ordered double perovskites ABiLiTeO₆ (A=Ba, Sr) were synthesized via solid state reaction route. Even though X-ray diffraction shows a cubic symmetry with space group Fm $\bar{3}$ m a detailed Raman analysis indicates a lower symmetry for all compounds possibly due to tilting of octahedra. The deconvolution of Raman spectra yields more than four Raman active modes which points out a lower symmetry for all these compounds. Fitting of Raman spectra shows number of first order Raman modes is 9 for BaBiLiTeO₆ and 7 for SrBiLiTeO₆. In accordance with observed number of bands and group theoretical predictions, symmetry of SrBiLiTeO₆ and that of BaBiLiTeO₆ is tetragonal (I4/m space group). BaBiLiTeO₆ and SrBiLiTeO₆ possess dielectric constant of 37 and 30 also dielectric loss of 0.028 and 0.024 respectively at 1 MHz.

Deconvoluted Raman spectra for BaBiLiTeO₆ ceramics. Experimental data are blue circles while the fitting curve is the red line. Green lines represent the phonon modes adjusted by Lorentzian curves. The cubic and tetragonal double perovskite structures are in inset.

Key words: Double Perovskite, Cation Ordering, Raman Spectra, Dielectric properties

References

[1] A. Dias et al., Chem. Mater. 2008, 20, 4347–4355